

THE ROLE OF MUSEUMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *Title much attention has been paid to the development and reorganization of museums in our country since independence. A special program has been developed for the development of museums. In particular, the “Uzbekmuseum” was established in 1999. The attention paid to museums has paved the way for the development of tourism. In addition, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Tourism” is an important guideline. Today tourism has become one of the sectors that take its place in the global economy.*

Key words: *Domestic tourism, museology, ceramics, history, international tourism, Uzbek tourism, cooperation.*

Аннотация: *Основная роль в статье отведена развитию и реорганизации музеев в нашей стране с момента обретения Узбекистаном независимости. Для развития музеев разработана отдельная программа. В частности, в 1999 году была создана организация «Узбекмузеум». Внимание к музеям проложило путь для развития туризма. Кроме того, законы Президента «О туризме» являются важными ориентирами. Сегодня туризм стал одним из секторов, занимающих свое место в мировой экономике.*

Ключевые слова: *внутренний туризм, музеология, керамика, история, международный туризм, узбекский туризм, сотрудничество.*

As each state moves forward, it is natural that it should always look at its history and strive to study and preserve existing customs, traditions and ancient monuments. In this regard, the role of museums is invaluable. Because they are an integrated system of culture, enlightenment, natural monuments from the past, which are preserved and displayed in accordance with current procedures. Our country is a paradise where many saints, scientists and geniuses were born, and the tourism industry is also widely developed. Although Uzbekistan is relatively new in the field of tourism, it has made progress in many areas. Our country has a great potential for the development of international tourism. After gaining independence, our state has developed new principles in the field of tourism. On July 27, 1992, by the decree of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Company “Uzbektourism” was established. The main task of the company was to create a national module for tourism development. Since 1993,

our country has been a member of the International Tourism Organization (UNWTO).

The establishment of new museums in our country, the history of the largest and most influential Timurids in the capital, the memory of the victims of repressions, the opening of the Archaeological Museum in Termez in the south of the country. Along with the establishment of new museums, special attention was paid to the radical improvement of the activities of all large and small museums, reorganization in the spirit of national independence [1, 44].

President of the Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, expressed the following views on the development of tourism: “Currently, one of the most promising sectors of the national economy is tourism. Uzbekistan is a country with great potential in the field of tourism. There are more than 7,300 cultural heritage sites in our country, and most of them are included in the UNESCO list. It is necessary to fully use the great potential for the development and acceleration of the “small pilgrimage” program, which includes visits to the holy shrines and monuments in the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara and Tashkent”[2].

Tourism is a new and promising link in the modern economy. Recently, raising the economy of our country to a higher level has risen to the level of public policy. It is becoming a mass movement to organize trips to historical cities, especially the so-called open-air museum city, which reflects our great and young past history. In this regard, a number of works are being carried out in Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva, our ancient cities, which are recognized as “open-air museums”.

The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, including the State Program “Year of Support of Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas and Technologies” also identifies the main tasks for the development of tourism. According to him, it is planned to stimulate the travel of locals across the country, create a favorable infrastructure for tourists, systematically develop domestic tourism through the promotion of tourism in the regions, create conditions for foreign tourists, expand their travel programs.

It includes the development of pilgrimage tourism as a promising area of the industry through the formation of appropriate infrastructure in the objects of material and cultural heritage of the country and the surrounding objects, the creation of appropriate conditions for religious ceremonies. In particular, Rishtan district of Fergana region is a region with a unique geographical location, tourism, labor potential, objects of cultural heritage and ceramics museums. Widely promoting the traditions of Rishtan pottery, the production of ceramic products is developing from year to year and is formed in a way that is typical of modern

styles. The school of pottery, which has been formed in the district over the years, is recognized all over the world and is of great interest to tourists visiting our country.

The State Committee for Tourism Development of the Fergana region, together with the relevant state economic bodies, is taking practical measures to increase the number of tourists by including the school of ceramics in the UNESCO Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity and improving the material and cultural heritage of the district.

In short, as a result of the high attention paid to museology, the following unprecedented work has been done in this area:

- A number of laws on the development and improvement of museology have been adopted and the organizational and legal framework for the activities of museums has been created.

- In order to effectively organize the work of the museum and coordinate the activities of museums, a fund was established.

- During the years of independence, a number of exhibitions have been organized in world museums to demonstrate to the world the material and cultural heritage preserved in the museums of Uzbekistan [3, 56].

In addition, it is planned to expand cooperation with international and national tourism organizations, build restaurants, purchase tourist vehicles, lease cultural heritage sites to entrepreneurs, organize balloon tours, organize rural tourism in the districts.

In the following years, the activities of museums and tourism have grown at a high rate, all of which has been achieved with great difficulty. I believe that the work done by our President in the face of these difficulties is of great importance, because they open many opportunities for our people by signing mutually beneficial and mutually beneficial agreements with different countries for the development and peace of our country.

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